

Health Issues Encountered by BPO Employees a Literature Study

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ABSTRACT

Business process outsourcing (BPO) in India is currently enduring high steady loss which is giving an alarming sign to many outsourcing organizations. BPO is the one sector where we can find more number of employee turnover for various reason. The study mainly focuses on numerous health issues encountered to outsourcing employees and its influence on employee attrition in BPO organization.

Keywords: Business process outsourcing, health hazards, employee issues, attrition

I. INTRODUCTION:

Although forceful wellbeing and health wars by their managers, two out of three professionals in business process outsourcing (BPO) organizations wait to live unfortunate ways of life, with chain-smoking and overwhelming drinking recorded as the significant indecencies among in excess of 600,000 laborers in the business. Huge numbers of the business' laborers, whose normal age extend from 26 to 28. Indian BPO industry has been developing significantly. In the previous couple of years, this industry has developed by 14% and created income of 14.1 billion USD. Scientists say that the development rate will triple in the years to come. In accordance with the Department of Health (DoH) plans to instruct business BPO representatives on wellbeing subjects as a few examinations uncover individuals working in the business experience the ill effects of different infections. In association with multinational organization One Johnson and Johnson (J&J), the DoH need to address the wellbeing difficulties of the BPO business, said to utilize in regards to 1.3 million representatives starting at 2016. BPO workers speak to a vital segment of our nation's workforce today, consequently it is basic that we address each

wellbeing hazard that they look in their work including absence of rest, work related pressure which they endeavor to balance with undesirable ways of life, among others and the normal and successive issues these are all hazard factors that can prompt genuine wellbeing conditions, for example, respiratory tract contaminations, gastrointestinal maladies, diabetes, cardiovascular ailments, and psychological well-being ailments

II. Objective of the study:

1. To study various health issues encountered by BPO employees

III. Purpose of the study:

Researchers around the world have comprehensively studied the concept, defining features, measurement methods and the approval of health issues. Even though health related issues are explained as various concepts in different countries, the concepts have common defining features. The researchers have developed different measurement methods and tools to analyze the occurrence of employee health. The current study aims to present a concise review of the common defining features of various health issues encountered by BPO employees.

IV. Methodology of the study

The study has done with the help of secondary data that are collected from research papers, online sources and journals.

V. Evolution of Business process outsourcing in India:

Amex and GE pioneered the trend of outsourcing to India by setting up facilities in Gurgaon, near Delhi, in the early 1990s. Some of the other early birds were

companies such as British Airways who have also been operating their back office in India since the mid-1990s. The early reasons for considering offshoring to India were centered around reducing costs and minimizing the effort spent on “non-core” activities.

VI. Definition of BPO:

Business process outsourcing (BPO) is the contracting of a specific business task, such as payroll, to a thirdparty service provider. Usually, BPO is implemented as a cost-saving measure for tasks that a company requires but does not depend upon to maintain their position in the marketplace. BPO is often divided into two categories: back office outsourcing which includes internal business functions such as billing or purchasing, and front office outsourcing which includes customer-related services such as marketing or tech support.

VII. Indian BPO:

In India, Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) is the top rising division of the ITES (Information Technology Enabled Services) industry. Factors such as economy of scale, business risk mitigation, cost advantage; utilization improvement and superior competency have all lead to the growth of the Indian BPO industry. Business process outsourcing in India, which started around the mid-90s, has now grown by leaps and bounds. India is now the world's favored market for BPO companies, among other competitors, such as, Australia, China, Philippines and Ireland. The BPO boom in India is credited to cheap labor costs and India's huge talent pool of skilled, English-speaking professionals. Research by the National Association of Software Services and Companies (NASSCOM) has revealed that quality orientation among leading BPO companies, 24/7 services, India's unique geographic location and the investor friendly tax structure in India have all made the BPO industry in India very popular.

VIII. Literature review:

Dr. Vinodh Kumar (2016) The examination center around India is a creating nation is assuming an unmistakable part in the administration area. The goal of the investigation is to investigate and discover the issues of these youngsters learning workers particularly the workplace and work weight on their psychological, physical and social wellbeing. The examination's discoveries show that there are extreme wellbeing risks that need quick consideration from

people and also government to distinguish the issues as well as to turn out with great wellbeing instruction and arrangement. Dinesh raj (2014) Call focus segment in India is a moderately new industry and one of the quickest developing parts driving business and development in present-day India today. While work in the business procedure outsourcing(BPO) segment has implied that youthful grown-ups are achieving their profession developments and budgetary objectives substantially sooner than previously, overviews and episodic proof demonstrate that employees in the BPO segment encounter abnormal amounts of pressure and its related issue, fundamentally because of its contemporary work settings. Shielding the strength of adolescents utilized in this new, developing economy turns into a word related wellbeing test to general wellbeing masters. Swaminathan and Rajkumar (2013) led an examination that concentrated on the level of pressure looked by the representatives which included individuals of various age gathering, calling, assortments of work, span or working hours and nature they work in. Stress is as yet a theme which isn't regularly talked about by the general population. An examination on association point of view by (Chimote and Srivastava. 2013) exposed that decreasing non-appearance and turnover, enhancing efficiency and picture, and guaranteeing steadfastness and maintenance are the advantages of WLB, This examination shows the fitting level at which a worker can perform at his maximum capacity. The investigation brings out three conditions in charge of business-related pressure. Part Overload, Role Self-remove, Role Stagnation. K. Karthikeyan (2009) Occupational medical issues are basic among BPO professionals. they are showed generally in mental and medical issues which straightforwardly mirror the personal satisfaction for laborers and abatement in efficiency. The investigation was done to evaluate the distinctive kinds of word related medical issues among the BPO experts the examination uncovers that larger part of them had muscle-skeletal issues, change in their nourishment propensities and their way of life was modified. The outcomes are talked about with the mediation of good settings of office and PC research center ergonomics are recommended. As indicated by Indradevi and Kamalapriya (2006), ladies working in call focuses are by and by influenced in the family and social life. Ladies working in call focuses confront worry because of different reasons like night shifts, and less self-sufficiency at work. At long last, the creators have recognized that poor workplace

additionally adds to pressure. V. P. Sudhashree (2005) long stretches of work, perpetual night shifts, fantastically high work targets, loss of character are these the dim mists that debilitate to deface the 'daylight' call focus industry in India? The odd timings and nature of work attaches individuals to a seat 9 h daily, perusing pre-scripted discussions on the telephone unendingly – regularly to furious clients from over the globe. Where each and every second of a employee's opportunity is recorded, estimated and naturally signed onto a PC for acclaim or blame on a week after week premise. Where strolling down to the idea of call focus work, the first is on the issue of character, and the second issue is the confinement looked by call focus representatives. Given the extreme contact between colleagues on a move, there will undoubtedly be some advancement of relational connections. At the point when the move changes, there is a sudden separation of relations. There is a time of aggregate separation both inside the workplace and without – since family lives get upset and contacts between relatives separation. The third issue is identified with the feelings of anxiety of representatives set to take a shot around evening time moves and given high targets – this may constrain some towards tranquilize manhandle or something to that affect like get up and go up pills and different medications to prop them up – particularly when youths have cash to enjoy – this is an extremely honest to goodness dread. As indicated by Preethi and Anu (2005) night shifts and ceaseless anxiety influence the wellbeing of ladies, and therefore, they can't worry about the twofold concern of work and family successfully. Majumdar (2004) notices that call center workers are under high degree strain to meet their amounts. ITES experts are high a result of long working hours and done without occasions, prompting lopsided characteristics in work and individual life. Work-life adjust involves worry for both the representatives and the businesses. It concerns the workers as far as their feeling of anxiety and its resultant results as far as sick wellbeing (both physical and mental), and it concerns the businesses, as the evil soundness of their representatives converts into diminished profitability and expanded non-appearance. Innovative progression and rivalry has just aggravated this issue of work-life irregularity.

IX. Study reveals that various health issues encountered by BPO employees

- Repetitive strain injury - Hands
- Frequent hyper tension (BP)

- Frequent Migraines and headaches
- Repetitive Eye-strain
- Vocal problems
- Digestive System Related Problems
- Depression
- Behavioral Issues
- Physical strain
- Weight loss
- Trouble in concentration
- Sleeping disorders
- Obesity
- Spondylitis / Back pain
- Suffering with thyroid problem
- Mensuration cycle problems
- Hearing disorders / Problems

X. Recommendations:

- Irrespective of the gender every employee should underwent for medical checkups every quarter.
- Take proper diet and take minimum seven hours sleep
- Do regular yoga and pranayama

XI. Conclusion:

The BPO's were very much interested in earning huge money with lot of strain in their work. The data presented in this study was a literature review on various health issues encountered in BPO industry. Organization has to take due care on employees health by conducting frequent health checkups. Creating awareness on health education and preventive and control measures has to take to overcome from it.

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